

Task 6.1 - Community Communication Platforms

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About this report

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Consortium members

Acronym	Partner
EMBL	EUROPEAN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY LABORATORY
BIOBYTE	BIOBYTE SOLUTIONS GMBH
HPCNOW	HPC NOW CONSULTING SL
UO	UNIVERSITETET I OSLO
UB	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA
ZBMED	INFORMATION CENTRE FOR LIFE SCIENCE
Rlcapacity	Rlcapacity
ALU-FR	ALBERT-LUDWIGS-UNIVERSITAET FREIBURG
EPFL	ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE

Table of Contents

About this report.....	2
Consortium members.....	2
Table of Contents.....	3
Project Overview.....	4
Preface.....	4
Community Communication Platforms.....	4
Objectives.....	4
Platforms and Channels.....	4
Use of Resources.....	5
Key Findings.....	5

Project Overview

The BioNT consortium is dedicated to providing a comprehensive training program and fostering a community for digital skills relevant to the biotechnology industry and biomedical sector. With a curriculum tailored for both beginners and advanced professionals, BioNT aims to equip individuals with the necessary expertise in handling, processing, and visualising biological data, as well as utilising computational biology tools. Leveraging the consortium's strong background in digital literacy training and extensive network of collaborations, BioNT is poised to professionalise life sciences data management, processing, and analysis skills.

Preface

This report documents the communication platforms established and maintained under Task 6.1 of Work Package 6 (Community and Capacity Building). It describes the channels, tools, and approaches used to facilitate communication within the consortium and with the wider public throughout the project. The intended readership encompasses consortium partners, the European Commission, and the wider public, including training communities, potential adopters of BioNT materials, and professionals with an interest in digital skills development for the biotechnology and biomedical sectors.

Community Communication Platforms

Objectives

The primary objectives of Task 6.1 were to:

- Keep communication channels clear, stable, and easy to use for all stakeholders
- Avoid fragmentation across too many platforms, ensuring a coherent and accessible presence

Platforms and Channels

The consortium adopted a focused approach to platform management, prioritising consolidation over expansion. The following platforms were established and maintained throughout the project:

Project Website

The BioNT website at biont-training.eu served as the main entry point for all project-related information. It provided access to training materials, upcoming events (most importantly, the BioNT Community Event), consortium partner profiles, community initiatives such as the Ambassador Programme, and openly accessible resources. The website template is published and maintained by ZB MED on behalf of the consortium.

LinkedIn

LinkedIn was used as the primary social media channel for public communication. It enabled the consortium to share project updates, announce training events, highlight outputs, and engage with the professional communities in the life sciences and biotechnology sectors. The channel was kept active and updated throughout the project duration.

Contact Address and Mailing List

A dedicated contact address at contact@biont-training.eu was established as the central point of contact for external enquiries. It was maintained and monitored consistently throughout the project.

Use of Resources

The allocated effort under this task primarily supported the operational maintenance and coordination of the project's communication infrastructure, including the website, contact channel, and LinkedIn presence. This also included iterative updates to the website and coordination activities related to community engagement, particularly in the context of the Ambassador Programme and the BioNT Community Event.

Key Findings

The approach taken in Task 6.1 reflected a deliberate strategic choice to maintain and consolidate existing platforms rather than creating new ones. This decision proved effective in:

- Reducing the administrative overhead associated with managing multiple fragmented channels
- Ensuring a consistent and recognisable presence for the BioNT project across all communication touchpoints
- Enabling reliable and timely updates to reach the intended audiences throughout the project lifecycle

All platforms were kept updated throughout the project, contributing to sustained visibility and stakeholder engagement in line with the dissemination and community-building goals of Work Package 6.